

Assessment of the pedestrian protection performance of a sandwich hood with architected lattice cores

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ABSTRACT

Pyramidal lattice composite structure possesses an excellent behaviour of ultra-low density, high stiffness and strength together with the advantage of multifunctionality, which could be promising for vehicle lightweight applications. In this study, a sandwich structured engine hood was proposed which comprises outer and inner steel panels together with a composite pyramidal lattice structure core (Fig.1). The pyramidal lattice core could be manufactured by slot assembly of strips cutting from flax fibre reinforced laminates. The pedestrian protection capability of engine hood was evaluated in finite element method. The architected pyramidal lattice sandwich structure in this study is proven to be feasible for a sandwich engine hood that could meet the Euro-NCAP HIC threshold of 1000. Moreover, the present study provides a good reference of lattice structures to similar application on car body panels with complex curvature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reducing energy consumption, together with environment protection has become the hot topic of automotive development. On average, 100 kg mass reduction achieved on a passenger car can save 0.315 L of fuel per 100 km and reduce 8 g of CO₂ exhaust per km. Lightweight design considering the fundamental function of automotive parts could significantly improve the current energy and environmental situation.

Several studies have been dedicated to the new design concepts of hood structures. Qing Zhou et al. focus on the sandwich hood and proposed an original hood design with ripple plate core. Yong Peng et al. evaluated the integral stiffness and pedestrian protection behavior of hoods with various inner panel designs and a sandwich hood with honeycomb core.

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Fig 1. Pyramidal lattice structure with complex curvature and its partial enlarged view

Fig.2: Unit cell of pyramidal lattice structure together with strut cross section

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Finite element modeling

Firstly, the mechanical properties of lattice unit cell, including elasticity constants and the stress-strain curves in three orthogonal directions were calculated and served as the material properties of homogenized core in LS-DYNA. Secondly, a sandwich engine hood model was constructed as illustrated in Figure 3 with homogenized lattice core possessing orthotropic mechanical properties, and the corresponding pedestrian protection capability was verified using head injury criteria (HIC) during head-to-car collision simulations.

Thirdly, a validated adult headform was used to impact the specific hood area according to the test protocol proposed by European New Car Assessment Program (Euro-NCAP). This work demonstrated that the lattice sandwich hoods herein have better pedestrian protection capability than the baseline hoods which was constructed without sandwich core. The responding curves of lattice sandwich hoods are similar to the ideal acceleration waveform proposed by Wu and Beaudet. The engine hood with pyramidal lattice core was then compared with the other two types of engine hoods: foam core sandwich structure and honeycomb core sandwich hood in condition of the same filling volume in terms of pedestrian head protection performance. The comparison results demonstrated that the lattice sandwich hood has the minimum HIC values.

Fig.3: (a) FE model for head impact test including the hood assembly and headform (b) FE model for hood assembly. the lattice core was homogenized as the green part of the figure.

2.2 Variable analysis

In the variable analysis section, two dimensionless variables of pyramidal lattice unit cell were selected as geometrical variables relative to the HIC value, namely the relative width of struts b/h and relative thickness of strips t/h as shown in Figure 2. To investigate the variation tendency of HIC value about these variables, similar simulations as above were conducted to figure out the corresponding pedestrian head protecting capability. Simulation result in Fig.4 provided the suitable geometrical variable combination of lattice structure.

Fig.4: Result of lattice sandwich hood geometrical variable analysis: HIC value of sandwich hoods in 9 geometrical variable combinations and 4 various impact locations.

3 CONCLUSION

An original lattice sandwich hood was proposed in this paper. A comparison of this hood design and baseline was carried out through FE method. The lattice sandwich hood obviously decreases the HIC level and shown a better pedestrian protection performance than the other 2

types of hoods. Furthermore, influence of material and geometric variables was also investigated the ideal combinations of lattice geometrical parameters to meet $HIC < 1000$ were figured out.

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